

A Study of Trauma and Mental Health of Women with Room by Emma Donoghue

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Abstract

This paper aims to develop a better understanding on feminist trauma and mental health of women with the help of literature with a special emphasis on women's literature. This research highlights how writers like Emma Donoghue have provided us with the insights of feminist trauma based on what they have experienced in their own life as well as what they have observed around them on how women were treated in their own homes by their own family members which leads to trauma and decline in their mental health.

With the help of trauma studies and various theories of trauma like Freud's psychoanalytic theory of trauma, this research work aims to portray the impact of trauma in literature and society by analyzing its psychological and cultural significance. With the help of literary trauma produced by writers who have portrayed trauma in their works as a main subject, we will be able to get a better overview of what feminist trauma is and how trauma and mental health are co-related to the incidents taking place in a person's life.

Keywords: Feminist trauma, mental health, women's literature, literary trauma, Theory of trauma

Introduction

A feminist trauma can be understood as a feeling of overwhelming emotions experienced due to some physical harm such as rape, domestic violence and many more by a women or marginalized gender due to any form of gender-based oppression, discrimination, or violence and how this inflicted violence has created an impact on the minds of the victim. This trauma is examined through a feminist lens to connect it with broader social and cultural structures such as

sexism, misogyny, and intersectional inequality. Literary trauma is a field which studies how literature deals with the personal and cultural aspects of trauma and engages with it. As a concept over the time trauma has developed a great deal of interest in literary studies and trauma theory represents a critical approach that enables new modes of reading and listening to a piece of literature.

If we talk about trauma in deeper sense, then Sylvia Plath can be taken as a good example, as she is one of the feminist authors who has depicted her trauma through her works, and which also discusses about her attempts of suicide done from 1953 till the time of her death in 1963. Her works like *Lady Lazarus* and *Bell Jar* we can drive a better understanding on trauma and mental health of women's. Sylvia Plath had a strained relationship with her family members due to which she never had a static relationship with which also implies how family plays a crucial role in maintaining mental health of an individual.

Emma Donoghue is an Irish Canadian playwright, novelist, screenwriter born on October 24, 1969, in Dublin, Ireland. Her novel *Room* was a finalist for the Booker prize and was also an international best seller. Her book *Room* was also adopted to feature as a film and was as well nominated for several awards in its visual mode as well. Her initiative of narrating the story from a child's perspective proves how trauma inflicted at younger age could change the entire perspective of growing up and living in the world. Their way of perceiving things and also differentiating between truth and lies are shaped differently from others.

Trauma as main theme in Room

Emma's novels are mostly influenced by real life incidents like her novel *Room* was influenced by dramatic frazil case which appeared around April 2008, where an Austrian women finally confessed to the police on how she was held captive for twenty four years by her own father in the basement area of the house and during the entire time period of her captivity she was raped multiple times by her own father which also proves to increase the reality of trauma described in the text.

Room by Emma Donoghue is considered to be one of the best fictional works to understand trauma through a child's perspective. Alongside trauma, it also takes into consideration the themes of attachment and loneliness as well. Jack is a five-year-old boy in the novel who had been living in the four walls of a room since his birth and was only having his mother as a companion. While his mother has lived here for seven years and when they escaped from the room after living there

for such an extended period, they perceive a different viewpoint about life. Jack has never been introduced to the outside world so when he encounters the life outside the four walls of those rooms, he finds it difficult to adjust with it, often craving for the life he had lived for the past five years in the room.

Whereas for Ma, the escape from the room gives her a new hope for life. Ma was kidnapped and sexually assaulted by a man named Nick for seven years. And when she was losing her will to live, the birth of Jack provided her with new hope and the will to live. Despite their confinement, Ma never forgets to provide Jack with an intricate view of the world outside like she once explained to him about the real world using the Television shows, “Listen. What we see on TV is . . . it’s pictures of real things.” That’s the most astonishing I ever heard. Ma’s got her hand over her mouth. “Dora’s real for real?” She takes her hand away. “No, sorry. Lots of TV is made-up pictures—like, Dora’s just a drawing—but the other people, the ones with faces that look like you and me, they’re real.” “Actual humans?” She nods. (Room, 2010: pg. 49) and when finally, they escaped the Room Jack started to perceive the life from different points, often comparing it with life he lived in that room, thus showing the signs of trauma. Ma was sexually abused and thus has a memory of rape and violence inflicted on her and when she escapes the room, she starts to show the signs of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). She develops anxiety issues and seems to be struggling with her identity and ego when she finally escaped. She grows fear of dirt and thus also keeps her son away from any insects or possible dirty areas.

She fears that anything might harm him and thus tries to protect him from any danger possible so that he doesn’t get exploited in any way like her. The seven years of captivity in a dark room has instilled a fear in her mind that contaminated places can harm you, and these signs are shown through her overprotective nature towards her son. This fear and feeling that anything which is not cleaned properly can harm you are also considered to be a sign of PTSD. Thus, Room by Emma Donoghue discovers the journey of Ma’s and Jack’s interpersonal growth, and proves to be an excellent work of trauma writing in modern fiction and the fact that this work was inspired from a real narrative provides it with more real depiction of trauma, it also classifies Emma Donoghue’s creativity as a trauma writer.

Implication of other theories in Room by Emma Donoghue

In the novel it is also been disclosed that Ma has given birth to a dead baby girl and how she was screaming for help, but old Nick was just there standing over and was not trying to help her, this instance can be taken as one of the reasons of Ma's overprotectiveness towards Jack. Ma did not want the Jack to go near to any place which could infect him. Even when she sent him to play with other children's she asked him to wear a Mask which could protect him for getting Ill. This instance can also be understood with the implication of Freud's theory where he argues that the painful loss of your loved ones can lead to a detachment from the society. He has argued that people who undergo such pain can lead to a display of physical and emotional disturbance and can be considered as the symptoms of Post traumatic stress disorder, which also proves that trauma does not limit to the physical beating or verbal abuse, but it can also be caused by a personal loss of an individual.

One of the western scholars has presented a theory on homelessness which can cause an overwhelming experience in individuals. He states that it is not necessary that every person can associate with any of the buildings in which they are living. One has a particular sense of peace and security that they can feel only if one is in a familiar environment. For an instance Ma was unable to develop a sense of peace even after living in that room for 7 years as it was not the place where she grew up. The place has witnessed her being harassed and the place only provided her with the feeling for homelessness, whereas for Jack, who has taken birth and lived in the same room for his five years of life has developed a sense of bonding with that room and as a result when they escaped the room he finds it difficult to cope up with outside world and often feels himself isolated from the world.

This sense of homelessness in two diverse ways for two different individuals living in the same environment provides an analysis on the ways of viewing the situation, and how a place can be a medium of both familiarity and unfamiliarity for two different individuals living in the same conditions. Ma's feeling of homelessness when she was captivated in that room and Jack's feeling of homelessness when he was introduced to the outer world contradict each other. This theory of Homelessness shows that not every person finds themselves connected with that place after living for longer time and sometimes a character who has not seen any outside world except that one

particular place can feel a sense of longing for that place for some particular time and at the end, they find themselves finally able to detach with that place.

Feud's theory of psychosexual stages can be applied to Jack's growth and individual development. According to his theory Jack is at its Phallic Stage which is stage of age range between 3-6 years, and he states that at such initial stages child's main focus is on their relationship with the one who is providing them with care and love. Similarly, Jack's attachment to Ma is intense, and he believes that Ma and the room in which they are living is their entire world, which reflects Feud's idea in the novel.

Conclusion

This paper in general has talked about Trauma as a main theme of Donoghue's novel. It provides us with an insight of violence faced by Ma in that room and how she was confined in those four walls for seven years of her life, where she also gave a birth to her son Jack who now serves as her constant companion. Ma's struggle highlights the long-term psychological trauma inflicted on her mind and the developments of PTSD symptoms in her, due to which she becomes overprotective for Jack ensuring that there should be no harm to him.

With the help of the novel, this paper has tried to underline the features of trauma and how the trauma in any form can have a significant impact in the lives of the individual, even if they have escaped to safer places. It also explains that trauma does not necessarily means harsh beatings, rape or any other form of violence, Trauma can also be caused mentally like if a person is kept caged for years similar to the case of Ma and Jack, and can give rise to the feelings of abandonment, detachment and homelessness, which are also considered as signs of trauma.

In total, this paper has explored the character's coping mechanism, development and their interpersonal growth which took place throughout the novel. With the help of other theories this study also provides the other views and perspectives of trauma and how characters of the novel have faced the issue and when they finally escaped from the confinement, they find it difficult to move forward with the outer world as the novel also talks about a fact that what we see for years , we assume it to be reality and when introduces to actual reality we find it difficult to adjust, as in the case of Jack, who believed that room is the actual world and when he was introduced to the outer world, he finds it difficult to leave his own space and adjust there but eventually he leaves his attachment for the room and starts his life in the outer world.

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